

Nonlinear Power System Load Identification Using Local Model Networks

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Abstract—This paper proposes a local model network (LMN) for measurement-based modeling of the nonlinear aggregate power system loads. The proposed LMN approach requires no pre-defined standard load model and uses measurement data to identify load dynamics. Furthermore, due to the interesting characteristics of the proposed approach, the LMN is able to have separate and independent linear and nonlinear inputs, determined by the use of prior knowledge. Trained by the newly developed hierarchical binary tree (HBT) learning algorithm, the proposed LMN attains maximum generalizability with the best linear or nonlinear structure. The previous values of the power system voltage and active and reactive powers are considered as the inputs of the LMN. The proposed approach is applied to the artificially generated data and IEEE 39-bus test system. Work on the field measurement real data is also provided to verify the method. The results of modeling for artificial data, the test system and real data confirm the ability of the proposed approach in capturing the dynamics of the power system loads.

Index Terms—Hierarchical binary tree (HBT) algorithm, local model networks, power system load modeling, system identification.

I. INTRODUCTION

ACCURATE load modeling plays a key role in the power system analysis, simulations and studies. Numerous researches have been conducted on the impacts of the power system loads on the system stability, particularly voltage stability and inter-area oscillations [1]–[4]. Furthermore, by accurate modeling of the power system loads the operational limits of the system can be precisely determined, while inaccurate load models may lead to system collapse or separation, due to the operation in unstable modes [5], [6]. Proper design of the automatic control systems and optimization of their configuration also depends on the correctness of the load models [5]. To stress the importance of the accurate power system load modeling, it is worth noting that the voltage collapse in Japan in 1987 was mainly occurred due to the reactive power characteristics of the air conditioning loads [7].

Load models, regardless of the modeling techniques, are divided into static load models and dynamic load models [6]. The static models are used when the analysis of the equilibrium conditions is required. They describe the relationship between the power consumption, voltage and frequency. However, in case of

stability analysis, dynamic load models are the common choice. They provide the additional advantage of representing time-sensitive behavior of the load [8]. In this paper, dynamic load modeling is pursued.

A. Brief Review on Power System Load Modeling Approaches

Exhibiting stochastic and time-varying behaviors, power system loads pose a complicated modeling challenge. Component-based and measurement-based approaches are two main categories of the load modeling methods [9]. The former requires prior knowledge about the load characteristics and components which add to the complexity of the modeling task due to the variety of the load components. However, the latter employs system identification techniques for load modeling by use of power system measurements. The measurement-based approach, adopted in this paper, provides a fine description of the real-time loads and their dynamic characteristics [6].

There is a variety of the measurement-based methods in the literature which transform the identification of the load models into an optimization process. Such methods usually consider a pre-defined standard model and then try to estimate the parameters of the model using an optimization technique. Adaptive simulated annealing [5], genetic algorithms and evolutionary computing [10] and population diversity-based genetic algorithms [11] are optimization techniques used for power system load identification. However, use of standard load models may not present the underlying phenomena of power system loads in all cases. The discretization procedure, performed in some of these approaches, like [5] and [6], can also introduce some errors into the identification process. Moreover, the model parameters could vary dramatically during different fault conditions and system re-configurations. In such conditions, re-estimation of the model parameters is required which may be time-consuming.

Computational intelligence (CI)-based modeling techniques, such as fuzzy systems and neural network, do not require such predefined standard load models. They can identify a process by the measurement data and without any specific information about the dynamics of the process. Furthermore, in case of a time-varying system or process, online learning algorithms can be employed to adapt to the new conditions quickly. A wide range of the identification applications have been reported for CI-based approaches [12]–[14]. However, application of the CI-based techniques for power system load identification has not been much pursued. There are limited publications in the literature which have focused on the power system load identification via artificial neural networks (ANN) [15], [16]. Some justifications for this may be the difficulties in proper setting of the learning parameters of the ANNs, slow

convergence rate and training failures due to the local minima [17].

B. Contributions and Highlights

To eliminate the aforementioned shortcomings, this paper proposes a local model network (LMN) for identification of the aggregate power system loads. The proposed LMN is composed of the local linear models (LLMs) and trained by the hierarchical binary tree (HBT) learning algorithm, which is fast in training and convergence and has a small number of training parameters. The LLMs are the most commonly used local models in the architecture of the LMNs, since they provide a good trade-off between the required number of the local models and their complexity. Besides, LLMs offer the possibilities of transferring parts of the mature field of linear control theory to the nonlinear world. The HBT learning algorithm performs fast input space partitioning through heuristic axis-orthogonal splits, and hence no nonlinear optimization for the direction of the splits is needed. In each iteration of the HBT algorithm, only parameters of the newly generated local models are computed and there is no need for the estimation of the parameters of the existing local models. As another advantage of the proposed approach, the linear and nonlinear inputs can be fed separately into the model (incorporation of the prior knowledge). This improves model's performance, accuracy and training speed. In brief, the contributions of this paper are listed below.

- The power system load identification is carried out using a local model network, which requires no pre-defined model and is able to deal with complex identification problems through *divide-and-conquer* strategy.
- A new learning algorithm is proposed for the LMN based on the concept of the decision tree, which is fast in training and has small number of adjustable parameters. No normalization of the validity functions is needed. Furthermore, in each iteration of the algorithm only the parameters of the newly generated local models are estimated.
- It is shown that incorporation of the prior knowledge about the power system dynamic load into the LMN enhances both training speed and model's accuracy. Furthermore, the model complexity is also reduced.
- Finally, it is worth noting that the proposed approach is a versatile tool which can be generally used in various other applications such as modeling, identification and forecasting.

The proposed approach will be applied for the nonlinear aggregate load identification using the artificially generated data, IEEE 39-bus test system and field measurement data, and compared to the other methods.

It is worth noting here that the proposed approach for the aggregate power system load modeling uses measurement data similar to the classical approaches presented in [5] and [6]. However, in [5] and [6], the measurement data were employed to estimate the parameters of a pre-defined model, while in this paper a new load model is constructed based on the

measurement data to describe the behavior of the aggregate power system load during steady-state and transient periods.

C. Paper Organization

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the structure of the LMN. The HBT learning algorithm is presented in Section III. The framework of the load identification and the procedure of incorporation of the prior knowledge are explained in Section IV. The proposed LMN model is evaluated based on three data sets, including artificially generated data, IEEE 39-bus test system and field measurement data in Section V. Finally, the findings of the paper are summarized in Section VI.

II. STRUCTURE OF THE LOCAL MODEL NETWORK

A. A Brief Review on LMNs

Local model networks (LMNs), also recognized as Takagi-Sugeno neuro-fuzzy systems, have received great attentions in the field of modeling, identification and prediction of the nonlinear dynamic systems [18]–[22]. LMNs can deal with the complex identification problems by dividing them into a set of smaller and simpler sub-problems. In fact, the main advantage of LMNs is that the identification of complex nonlinear processes is alleviated by the integration of the structured knowledge about the process [19]. The ability to describe different operating regimes of a system or process by different local models (LMs) has made LMNs appealing to many researchers to date [20]–[22].

The pioneering local linear neuro-fuzzy (LLNF) model, originally proposed by Nelles [18], is one of the most popular LMNs for identification and prediction of nonlinear systems [22], [23]. The LLNF model is trained by the local linear model tree (LOLIMOT) learning algorithm, which is based on a *divide-and-conquer* strategy [22]. Despite successful application of the LLNF and LOLIMOT learning algorithms, they suffer several drawbacks. First, due to the normalization of validity functions in each iteration of the LOLIMOT algorithm, the normalization side effects such as reactivation may occur. Second, in each iteration of the learning procedure the parameters of the new and all existing local models and their validity functions should be re-estimated. This slows down the learning procedure when the dimension of the input space is high or large number of the local models is required.

Later, the mentioned drawbacks were overcome by using the hierarchical tree learning algorithms [24]. The developed hierarchical tree algorithms eliminated normalization side effects and the need to re-estimate parameters of all existing LMs and their validity functions in each iteration. However, the hierarchical tree algorithms applies the axis-oblique partitioning of the input space and nonlinear optimization procedures are required to determine optimal direction for the axis-oblique split [24]. Therefore, the speed of the algorithm is reduced for high-dimensional input spaces.

This paper proposes an LMN, composed of the LLMs and trained by the heuristic HBT learning algorithm, for the identification of the power system loads. The proposed approach is fast in training and convergence and has a small number of adjustable parameters. During the training of the LMN with HBT algorithm, normalization side effects are avoided and nonlinear optimization of the split direction is not required.

B. Structure of the LMN

In essence, the LMNs operate based on the interpolation of the local models (LMs), weighted by their associated validity functions. The output of an LMN with p inputs $\underline{u} = [u_1 \ u_2 \ \dots \ u_p]^T$ and M local models can be expressed as

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i=1}^M h_i(\underline{u}) \Phi_i(\underline{u}) \quad (1)$$

where $h_i(\cdot)$ is an arbitrary function describing i th local model (LM_i), Φ_i is the corresponding validity function of the LM_i and is the LMN's output. The validity functions determine the validity region of their corresponding LMs. They can be interpreted as the operating point dependent weighting factors, which determine the contribution of their associated LMs to the final output. The LMN in (1) can be interpreted as a fuzzy inference system with M rules, where $\Phi_i(\underline{u})$ and $h_i(\underline{u})$ represent the rule premises and associated rule consequents, respectively.

In order to have a smooth transition between the local models, the validity functions are smooth and take their values between 0 and 1. Furthermore, the validity functions must form a partition of unity to have reasonable interpretation of the local models

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \Phi_i(\underline{u}) = 1. \quad (2)$$

Usually, when the validity functions do not automatically sum up to 1, the partition of unity is achieved through normalization. Hence, for M local models, the validity functions are calculated by

$$\Phi_i(\underline{u}) = \frac{\mu_i(\underline{u})}{\sum_{i=1}^M \mu_i(\underline{u})} \quad (3)$$

where μ_i are the multidimensional membership functions. While the normalization denominator in (3) enforces that the validity functions Φ_i form a partition of unity, but it can result in unexpected and undesirable normalization side-effects, such as reactivation and unsatisfactory extrapolation behavior, which will be clarified in more details by an illustrative example in Section III-C.

The structure of an LMN with p inputs and M local models is shown in Fig. 1. In this figure, each local model and its associated validity function, realize a neuron. The LMN

described by (1) and shown in Fig. 1 features two favorable properties: first, it can have independent inputs for the rule premise (validity functions) and the rule consequent (local models) parts. This property can be effectively utilized to incorporate the prior knowledge about the process to be modeled, identified or predicted. The model in (1) can be rewritten as

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i=1}^M h_i(\underline{x}) \Phi_i(\tilde{\underline{x}}) \quad (4)$$

where \underline{x} and $\tilde{\underline{x}}$ are the input variables in the consequent and premise spaces, respectively. Second, arbitrary functions, e.g., linear, polynomial or other nonlinear functions, can be integrated as local models into the LMN.

Local linear models (LLMs) are by far, the most commonly used local models in the architecture of LMNs, since they provide a good trade-off between the required number of local

Fig. 1. Structure of the LMN with p inputs and M local models.

models and their complexity. Besides, the LLMs offer the possibilities of transferring parts of mature field of linear control theory to the nonlinear world [24].

If the LLMs are used in the structure of an LMN, the input LM_i , $i = 1, \dots, M$ with p_x

$$h_i(\underline{x}) = \theta_{i,0} + \theta_{i,1}x_1 + \dots + \theta_{i,p_x}x_{p_x}$$

where $\underline{\theta} = [\theta_{i,0} \ \theta_{i,1} \ \dots \ \theta_{i,p_x}]^T$ is the parameter vector of the LM_i and p_x is the dimension of the consequent space. For a local linear model, the number of parameters of the local model would be

variables is expressed by

$$n_{p_x} = p_x + 1. \quad (5)$$

$$n_{p_x} = p_x + 1. \quad (6)$$

For the estimation of the parameters of LLMs, a simple but efficient weighted least square (WLS) algorithm is utilized. In WLS algorithm it is assumed that validity functions are determined a priori. The WLS estimation is carried out based on the minimization of local error of each local model and for N training samples

$$\min_{\theta_i} \left\{ I_i = \sum_{j=1}^N \Phi_i(\hat{x}(j)) e(j) \right\}, \quad i = 1, \dots, M \quad (7)$$

where $e(j) = y(j) - \hat{y}(j)$ and $\underline{y} = [y(1), \dots, y(N)]$ are N target outputs. The regression matrix, associated with the i th local model for the N training samples can be constructed as

$$\underline{R}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_1(1) & x_2(1) & \dots & x_{p_x}(1) \\ 1 & x_1(2) & x_2(2) & \dots & x_{p_x}(2) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_1(N) & x_2(N) & \dots & x_{p_x}(N) \end{bmatrix}_{N \times n_{p_x}} \quad (8)$$

Given the regression matrix in (8), the solution of the weighted least square problem in (7) is expressed by

$$\theta_i = (\underline{R}_i^T \underline{D}_i \underline{R}_i)^{-1} \underline{R}_i^T \underline{D}_i \underline{y} \quad (9)$$

where \underline{D}_i is the $N \times N$ diagonal weighting matrix

$$\underline{D}_i = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_i(\hat{x}(1)) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \Phi_i(\hat{x}(2)) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \Phi_i(\hat{x}(N)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Fig. 2. Hierarchical model structure with 5 local models (at leaves).

Hence, the parameters of the local polynomial functions can be estimated using (9). It should be noted that for the WLS estimation, it is assumed that the validity functions are known in advance. In fact, the validity functions are constructed by the HBT algorithm, introduced in the next section.

III. HIERARCHICAL BINARY TREE LEARNING ALGORITHM

The hierarchical binary tree (HBT) learning algorithm is a heuristic tree-construction algorithm, motivated by the local linear model tree (LOLIMOT) learning algorithm [22]. The idea of binary tree is based on the concept of the decision tree,

introduced by Breiman *et al.* [25]. The HBT learning algorithm tries to hierarchically partition the input space into the hyper-rectangular sub-domains by axis-orthogonal splits. In each iteration of the algorithm, the worst-performing local model is divided into two halves. Therefore two new local models are generated and their associated validity functions are determined. This procedure continues until the desirable performance is achieved. The hierarchical partitioning of the input space and the hierarchical binary tree, which constitute the core part of the HBT algorithm, are explained in the next subsection.

A. Hierarchical Partitioning of Input Space

The architecture of the HBT algorithm is represented by a hierarchical binary tree example, shown in Fig. 2. In this architecture, each node corresponds to the partition of the input space into two areas by the splitting function $\Psi_i(\hat{x})$ and its counterpart

. It is seen that two splitting functions automatically sum up to unity; therefore no normalization is needed and its undesirable side effects, such as reactivation in LOLIMOT [18], are avoided.

The partitioned regions are further sub-divided by succeeding nodes, if any, and the binary tree ends with a set of end nodes, called leaves. Each leaf represents a local model and its contribution to the overall model output is given by its validity function, computed by multiplication of all splitting functions from the root of the tree to the corresponding leaf. For the binary tree in Fig. 2 with nine nodes and five leaves, the validity functions can be expressed as

$$\Phi_4(\hat{x}) = (1 - \psi_2(\hat{x})) (1 - \psi_1(\hat{x})) \quad (11)$$

$$\Phi_5(\hat{x}) = (\psi_2(\hat{x})) (1 - \psi_1(\hat{x})) \quad (12)$$

$$\Phi_7(\hat{x}) = \psi_3(\hat{x}) \psi_1(\hat{x}) \quad (13)$$

$$\Phi_8(\hat{x}) = (1 - \psi_6(\hat{x})) (1 - \psi_3(\hat{x})) \psi_1(\hat{x}) \quad (14)$$

$$\Phi_9(\hat{x}) = \psi_6(\hat{x}) (1 - \psi_3(\hat{x})) \psi_1(\hat{x}) \quad (15)$$

It can be easily investigated that

$$\sum_{i=\{4,5,7,8,9\}} \Phi_i(\hat{x}) = 1. \quad (16)$$

If the validity functions are known, the model output can be computed as the sum of local models weighted by their validity functions

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i \in \ell} h_i(\underline{x}) \Phi_i(\hat{x}) \quad (17)$$

where ℓ is the set of indices of the leaf nodes. In Fig. 2, $\ell = \{4, 5, 7, 8, 9\}$.

Sigmoid splitting functions are suitable for heuristic axis-orthogonal partitioning of the input space, since proper

$$LM_i \quad i = 1, \dots, M$$

$$(LM_{wt})$$

multiplication of sigmoid functions can easily generate the local validity functions. A sigmoid splitting function is expressed as

$$\psi_i(\tilde{x}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\sigma_i(w_{i,0} + w_{i,1}\tilde{x}_1 + \dots + w_{i,p_{\tilde{x}}}\tilde{x}_{p_{\tilde{x}}})}} \quad (18)$$

where $p_{\tilde{x}}$ is the dimension of premise space, the direction vector $\underline{w}_i = [w_{i,1} \dots w_{i,p_{\tilde{x}}}]^T$ sets the direction of split, position parameter $w_{i,0}$ determines the position of the split and the smoothness parameter σ_i determines the smoothness of the split.

The presented hierarchical structure has the appealing property of being fractal. In fact, each node itself can be interpreted as a root for a hierarchical sub-model. This is an interesting feature, since if a model performs well, for whatever reason, at a high level (i.e., partitioning of whole input space), then it is reasonable to employ it for the sub-models as well [18]. In the described hierarchical structure, each node includes sub-models of the same type, which again include sub-sub-models of the same type, until the maximum depth is reached.

B. Learning Algorithm

The HBT learning algorithm works based on the structure of the hierarchical binary tree, introduced in previous sub-section. In each iteration of HBT algorithm, the worst-performing local model (LM_{wt}) is determined using loss function (7). Then the validity region (premise space) of the LM_{wt} is divided into two equal hyper-rectangles through axis-orthogonal splits. The divisions in all dimensions of the premise space are tried and the best division, which leads to the highest improvement in model performance, is performed. Since the splits are axis-orthogonal, all entries of the direction vector, except the one which corresponds to the division dimension, are zero. For instance, if division in 2nd dimension is intended, the direction vector would be $\underline{w}_i = [0 \ 1 \ \dots \ 0]^T_{1 \times p_{\tilde{x}}}$. Hence, the direction vector of the splitting function can be determined heuristically and without running any time-consuming nonlinear optimization procedure. The positioning parameter $w_{i,0}$ is set equal to the center of the LM_{wt} at the split dimension and the smoothness parameter is proportional to the length of the newly-generated hyper-rectangle.

Once the splitting function $\Psi_i(\tilde{x})$ is determined, its counterpart, $1 - \Psi_i(\tilde{x})$, can be easily computed.

When the splitting functions and consequently the validity functions are determined, the parameters of the corresponding local models can be estimated by WLS algorithm through (9). The HBT learning algorithm is summarized as follows:

- 1- *Start with the initial model:* Set, start with a single LM whose validity function covers the whole input space and estimate the model parameters using (9).
- 2- *Find the worst LM:* Calculate a loss function defined by (7), for each of, and find the worstperforming local model

- 3- *Check all divisions:* The validity region of the LM_{wt} must be divided into two equal hyper-rectangles (two new validity regions), in all of dimensions.

3-(a) *Construct splitting functions:* For each of $p_{\tilde{x}}$ divisions, a splitting function must be determined. The positioning parameter is set equal to the center of the LM_{wt} at the split dimension, all entries of the direction vector, except the one which corresponds to the division dimension, are zero and smoothness parameter is simply set proportional to the length of the newly-generated hyper-rectangle. Once the splitting function is determined calculate its counterpart .

3-(b) *Compute validity functions:* Determine the validity functions of two newly-generated validity regions by multiplication of all splitting functions from the root of the tree to the corresponding leaf. 3-(c) *Estimate local models parameters:* Only parameters of the two LMs, corresponding to the two newlygenerated validity regions, must be estimated using (9) and finally the loss function for the current overall model must be computed. Other existing local models remain unchanged.

- 4- *Find the best division:* The best LMs related to the lowest loss function value must be determined. The number of LMs is incremented: $M \rightarrow M + 1$. If the termination criterion, e.g., a desired level of validation error or model's complexity, is met then stop, otherwise go to step 2.

Maximum generalization and noteworthy modeling performance are among the salient features of the model identified by HBT learning algorithm.

C. Illustrative Example

The detailed descriptions of the LMN and HBT algorithm have been presented in Sections II and III, respectively. However, in order to shed light on the advantages of the proposed approach and make a comparison to the LOLIMOT algorithm [22], an illustrative identification example is provided here. In this example, the following nonlinear system is identified using both proposed LMN and LLNF model:

$$y = \frac{0.01 + 0.1u}{0.01 + 0.1u + 1.5u^2}. \quad (19)$$

For the purpose of identification, u is used as the input to model output . To generate identification data, 1000 inputoutput samples are generated within , where the first 600

TABLE I
COMPARISON BETWEEN LOLIMOT AND HBT LEARNING ALGORITHMS

Method	Training RMSE	Test MAPE
LLNF + LOLIMOT	1.4×10^{-3}	0.0261
LMN + HBT	1.16×10^{-3}	0.0068

samples are used as training data and the remaining 400 samples serve as the test data set.

Table I presents the training and testing root mean square errors (RMSE) obtained by the proposed HBT learning algorithm as well as the LOLIMOT learning algorithm. It is obvious that both learning algorithms have comparable performances in terms of training. However, the performances are totally different for testing data, which require extrapolation (since the testing data fall outside the range of training data). As presented in Table I, the HBT learning algorithm has superior performance to the LOLIMOT algorithm. This is due to the better extrapolation of the LMN trained by the HBT algorithm. In fact, the favorable extrapolation behavior comes from avoiding the normalization and thus eliminating its side-effects.

To explore this issue in more details, the validity functions obtained by the LOLIMOT and the HBT algorithms in the third iteration are shown in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b), respectively. In the LLNF model with LOLIMOT algorithm, the validity functions do not form a partition of unity automatically and therefore normalization is carried out according to (3). However, the normalization brings about undesirable reactivations of the validity functions. As seen from Fig. 3(a), the reactivation happens for the validity functions obtained by LOLIMOT at two points around and 2.5. For instance, it is expected that for the inputs larger than 0, the third validity function, Φ_3 , is the dominant validity function. However, it is seen that the first validity function, Φ_1 , is unexpectedly reactivated for the inputs larger than 2.5 and contributes to the output dominantly. Such reactivations downgrade the extrapolation performance of the LLNF model. The validity functions obtained by the HBT algorithm are shown in Fig. 3(b). Clearly, no reactivation occurs.

IV. LOAD IDENTIFICATION FRAMEWORK

A. Identification Procedure

For the purpose of measurement-based identification, a

$$P(k) = f_P(P(k-1), \dots, P(k-n_P), V(k-1), \dots, V(k-n_{VP})) \quad (20)$$

$$Q(k) = f_Q(Q(k-1), \dots, Q(k-n_Q), V(k-1), \dots, V(k-n_{VQ})) \quad (21)$$

$P(k)$, $Q(k)$ and $V(k)$ are active power, reactive power and load voltage at time instant k , respectively. f_P and f_Q sent nonlinear functions describing active and reactive dynamic loads, respectively. n_P and n_{VP} denote the largest delay values general dynamic load model can be expressed as a function of

previous values of load power and voltage where

the active power and load voltage, respectively, used as the inputs for modeling active dynamic load, while n_Q and n_{VQ} indicate the largest delayed values of the reactive power and load

Fig. 3. (a) Validity functions obtained by LOLIMOT. (b) Validity functions obtained by HBT for the illustrative example.

Fig. 4. Serial-parallel active load identification by LMN.

voltage, respectively, used as the inputs for modeling reactive dynamic load. In this paper, it is focused on constructing nonlinear functions f_P and f_Q using the proposed LMN. The block diagram of the active dynamic load identification is shown in Fig. 4. Similar diagram may be also drawn for reactive dynamic load identification.

B. Incorporation of Prior Knowledge

According to Fig. 1, the input vectors of LLMs and the validity functions can be apart and independent from each other. Clearly, the inputs which influence the process linearly can be fed into the LLMs, while nonlinear variables are suitable as validity functions' inputs. The separation of the input variables should be conducted by the prior knowledge about the process to be identified. This procedure of variable separation not only improves the overall performance of the LMN, but also speeds

up the learning of the model due to the lower dimension of the rule premise and rule consequent input spaces, compared to an LMN without input variable separation.

For the purpose of power system load identification, linear and nonlinear input variables should be selected prior to LMN training. Recall that the input variables for load identification are system voltage and active/reactive power while the output variable is the active/reactive power. To do this, a standard dynamic model of the power system load is used [6]. Based on this model, which is stated below, the linear or nonlinear relationship between inputs and output can be inferred:

$$\dot{x}(t) = -\frac{x(t)}{T_p} + P_0 \left[\frac{V(t)}{V_0} \right]^{N_{ps}} - P_0 \left[\frac{V(t)}{V_0} \right]^{N_{pt}} \quad (22)$$

$$P(t) = \frac{x(t)}{T_p} + P_0 \left[\frac{V(t)}{V_0} \right]^{N_{ps}} \quad (23)$$

$$\dot{z}(t) = -\frac{z(t)}{T_q} + Q_0 \left[\frac{V(t)}{V_0} \right]^{N_{qs}} - Q_0 \left[\frac{V(t)}{V_0} \right]^{N_{qt}} \quad (24)$$

$$Q(t) = \frac{z(t)}{T_q} + Q_0 \left[\frac{V(t)}{V_0} \right]^{N_{qs}} \quad (25)$$

where P_0 , Q_0 and V_0 are nominal active power, nominal reactive power and voltage magnitudes, respectively, T_p and T_q indicate the time constant for internal state variables $x(t)$ and $z(t)$, respectively, and N_{ps} , N_{qs} , N_{pt} and N_{qt} are steady-state and transient voltage indices, respectively. The models presented above can capture the dominant nonlinear steady-state behavior of the load as well as load recovery and overshoot. According to (22)–(25), the system voltage affects the active power nonlinearly. So, system voltage is selected as the input for validity functions. Furthermore, the autocorrelation analysis of the measured active and reactive load power revealed that their previous values have a linear relationship with their current value. Hence, the previous values of the load power are considered as the input variables of the LLMs.

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section is devoted to evaluate the proposed LMN performance through three case studies, namely identification of power system load using artificial data, load identification based on simulations on IEEE 39-bus system and load identification using real data measured by a phasor measurement unit (PMU) installed on a load bus.

To provide some comparisons for better evaluation of the proposed approach, the NARMAX model proposed by Jazayeri *et al.* in [6] will be implemented and used in case studies. Furthermore, to investigate the impact of incorporation of prior knowledge on dynamic load identification accuracy, the results of identification by LMN with and without prior knowledge will be reported in all case studies.

For the numerical assessment of the identification accuracy, the following error criteria are used and computed:

- Root mean square error (RMSE)

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T (y(k) - \hat{y}(k))^2}. \quad (26)$$

Mean absolute percentage error (MAPE%)

$$\text{MAPE\%} = \frac{100}{T} \sum_{n=1}^T \left| \frac{y(k) - \hat{y}(k)}{y(k)} \right| \quad (27)$$

$y(k)$ and $\hat{y}(k)$ are actual and LMN's outputs at sample k , respectively, and T is the number of the predicted samples.

where

Fig. 5. Actual versus identified active load power for artificial test data.

A. Artificially Generated Data

To generate artificial data, the standard models described by (22)–(25) are used. Since the models for active and reactive loads are similar to each other, only the active power data will be generated using model described by (22) and (23) for the purpose of identification. For this model, the parameters were set to $[T_p, N_{ps}, N_{pt}] = [0.8, 1.2, 1.8]$ and voltage (V_0) and nominal power were set to 1 per unit. The model was simulated in MATLAB/SIMULINK environment using a voltage signal with uniform distribution between 0.9 and 1.1 p.u., which is reasonable since those values are the typical limits on per-unit voltage, and the sampling period of 1 s. The model output was then contaminated with white Gaussian noise with zero mean and variance of 0.002 to simulate the measurement error. The standard model was then executed to generate 2000 data points, which were used for evaluation of the proposed LMN.

A voltage dip was also simulated in the test samples only, which was not available in the training data. This was simulated to assess the proposed approach performance in case of such abnormal system conditions. The first 1700 samples were used to train the LMN and the remaining 300 samples were kept for evaluation of the trained LMN. In order to find the best structure of the LMN as well as the most proper delay values for input variables, the last 10 percent of the training data were used as validation data set. It was found the model has lowest validation

RMSE for \hat{A} and \hat{B} . Accordingly, the model has 4 input variables totally. These inputs were used for modeling the active and reactive load in the next two case studies as well.

The actual and estimated active powers for test samples are shown in Fig. 5. It is interesting to see that the proposed approach has accurately modeled the simulated power even when the abnormal condition happened. Numerical results for this case study are presented in Table II. While both LMNs with and without prior knowledge showed better performance compared to NARMAX mode, but the difference is negligible (note the RMSEs). Interestingly, the LMN with prior knowledge has also better accuracy with respect to the LMN without prior knowledge. This confirms the desirable effect of incorporating prior knowledge about the dynamic load into the modeling procedure.

B. IEEE 39-Bus Test System

In the second study, dynamic load modeling is pursued using simulations on IEEE 39-bus test system. It includes a ten-machine test system with 46 branches and 19 loads. In this case study, the load identification is carried out for load bus 28. On

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON FOR ARTIFICIAL TEST DATA

Method	RMSE	MAPE%
NARMAX	0.0079	0.2040
LMN without prior knowledge	0.0073	0.1866
LMN with prior knowledge	0.0058	0.1072

Fig. 6. Load voltage on bus 27 during transient in IEEE 39-bus test system.

Fig. 7. Actual and identified active load power during transient in IEEE 39-bus test system.

Two different simulations were performed for training the LMN and testing its performance. For generating training data, a short circuit was applied on bus 27 and then it was cleared after five cycles. The load data at bus 28 were recorded during this transient. During this simulation, 824 data sample were produced. These data were used to train the LMN with HBT algorithm. Next, for testing the performance of the trained LMN, 3-phase short circuit was applied on the line between bus 26 and bus 28, close to the bus 26 and cleared after eight cycles. The generated data were used to evaluate the performance of the LMN. The load voltage, actual and identified active and reactive loads for the test simulation are shown in Figs. 6–8, respectively. It is seen from Figs. 7 and 8 that the proposed LMN has modeled the dynamic load during the steady-state and especially transient periods (magnified by the bottom-right boxes) with a high accuracy. Table III presents the numerical evaluations of and comparisons between the NARMAX mode, LMN without prior knowledge and LMN with prior knowledge. It is seen that the LMN with prior knowledge has the best performance. Also, in contrast to the previous case study, the difference between performance of the LMNs and the NARMAX model is noticeable.

To have more detailed assessments of the proposed LMN's performance and to provide statistical evaluations, similar simulations were carried out for all other load buses (i.e., the

Fig. 8. Actual and identified reactive load power during transient in IEEE 39-bus test system.

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON FOR IEEE 39-BUS TEST SYSTEM

Method	RMSE (p.u.)		MAPE%	
	P	Q	P	Q
NARMAX	0.0322	0.0311	0.3988	3.0434
LMN without prior knowledge	0.0086	0.0039	0.1064	1.2409
LMN with prior knowledge	0.0073	0.0018	0.0636	0.8981

TABLE IV
STATISTICAL PERFORMANCE EVALUATION FOR IEEE 39-BUS TEST SYSTEM

this bus, a static load was connected and the dynamic load was considered by including induction motors.

Method	RMSE (average)		RMSE (variance)	
	P	Q	P	Q
NARMAX	0.0318	0.0321	6.4×10^{-5}	2.0×10^{-5}
LMN without prior knowledge	0.0081	0.0036	2.2×10^{-6}	1.1×10^{-6}
LMN with prior knowledge	0.0070	0.0017	9.0×10^{-7}	8.7×10^{-7}

remaining 18 load buses) and the training and testing samples were generated. For each simulation, the LMN was trained using training data and then applied to the corresponding test data. Finally, the test RMSE was computed for each simulation, resulting in 18 values for test RMSE each corresponding to a simulation. To provide the statistical evaluation, the mean and variance of the test RMSE values are presented in Table IV. For the purpose of comparison, the results of the NARMAX are also reported. Based on the presented results, the LMNs show negligible variance of the RMSE, which is about one-tenth of the RMSE variance obtained by the NARMAX model. The results of the presented diverse simulations indicate that the proposed LMN preserves its performance in different simulations. Hence, it may be concluded that the proposed approach is a dependable tool for power system load identification.

C. Field Measurement Data

Successful application of the proposed LMN for the power system load modeling was shown through the artificial data and IEEE 39-bus test system in the two previous case studies. However, things can be totally different for the real data. Hence, evaluation of the identification approach using field data is necessary. For this purpose the field data, measured by a PMU installed in a major load bus in Brisbane, Australia, were em-

Fig. 9. Load voltage for field measurement data.

Fig. 10. Actual and identified active load power for field measurement data.

Fig. 11. Actual and identified reactive load power for field measurement data.

ployed. The measurements include system voltage and current phasors, sampled at 0.02 s intervals. These data were used to calculate the active and reactive power offline. The total data contain 1000 samples; the first 500 samples were used for training the LMN and the last 500 samples were used as test data set.

The load voltage for the test samples is shown in Fig. 9 while the actual and identified active and reactive load powers are depicted in Figs. 10 and 11, respectively. It is seen that the identified load by the LMN has successfully followed the fast variations of the actual load. For the numerical analysis, the RMSE and MAPE for the test samples, obtained by NARMAX model, LMN without prior knowledge and LMN with prior knowledge are presented in Table V. One can easily notice the superior performance of both LMNs over the NARMAX model. Furthermore, the desirable effect of incorporation of prior knowledge can also be inferred from Table V.

D. Computational Burden

Investigation of training/estimation time for the implemented approaches is also of interest. Table VI summarizes the training/estimation time for NARMAX model, LMN without prior knowledge and LMN with prior knowledge in each case study. The fast training speed of the proposed local model

TABLE V
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON FOR FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Method	RMSE (MW)		MAPE%	
	P	Q	P	Q
NARMAX	0.0161	0.0155	0.0879	0.2688
LMN without prior knowledge	0.0065	0.0051	0.0341	0.2059
LMN with prior knowledge	0.0057	0.0043	0.0259	0.1784

TABLE VI
COMPARISON OF TRAINING/ESTIMATION TIME (IN SECONDS)

Method	Artificial data	IEEE 39-bus (average value for all simulations)	Field data
NARMAX	15.33	14.41	12.43
LMN without prior knowledge	1.66	1.63	1.38
LMN with prior knowledge	0.98	0.97	0.83

TABLE VII
COMPLEXITY COMPARISON BETWEEN LMNS WITH AND WITHOUT
PRIOR KNOWLEDGE (FIELD MEASUREMENT DATA)

Method	Premise parameters	Consequent parameters	Total parameters
LMN without prior knowledge	16	10	26
LMN with prior knowledge	28	25	53

networks compared to NARMAX model is noticeable. One can also observe the much less computational burden achieved by the incorporation of prior knowledge. In fact, incorporation of the prior knowledge has reduced the curse of dimensionality in both premise and consequent spaces and thus the overall number of the parameters of the LMN. Table VII presents a comparison between the LMNs with and without incorporation of prior knowledge for the field measurement data case study. Obviously, the LMN with prior knowledge totally includes 26 parameters while the LMN without prior knowledge has 53 parameters (more than twice). Hence, the reduction in model complexity is remarkable.

It is also worth noting that the computational burdens of similar order are expected in case of larger power systems. The computation time is directly dependent on the number of training samples, number of LMNs' input variables as well as the number of local models required for accurate load modeling. In all three case studies, presented in this paper, identical input variables were used and the numbers of local models were almost the same. Besides, the number of training samples ranged from 500 to 1700 samples. It is seen, based on the results presented in Table VI, that the complexities of the LMNs in all case studies are comparable. Hence, we can hopefully expect that similar computational burdens would be imposed in case of larger power systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed an LMN, trained by the HBT algorithm for nonlinear power system load identification. The proposed LMN easily allows for incorporation of prior knowledge by providing separate input spaces for rule consequent and rule premise parts. The HBT learning algorithm heuristically partitions the input space into smaller sub-domains by axis-orthogonal splits. In each partitioning, the validity functions automatically form a unity partition and therefore no normalization side effects occur.

The developed approach was applied to three different case studies. In the first case study the artificial data were used and the LMN successfully identified the load dynamics. A voltage sag was also considered in this case study which again showed the noticeable ability of the proposed approach in load modeling, even during abnormal conditions. In the second case study, short-circuit transients were applied on IEEE 39-bus test system and the LMN was employed to identify the dynamic behavior of the nonlinear load during the transients. A third case study was also considered using field measurements data,

collected from a load bus to validate the proposed method. The proposed LMN with HBT learning algorithm identified the measured active power with remarkable accuracy. Influence of the input variable separation was also analyzed and it was concluded that such a procedure increases model training speed as well as its accuracy. Finally, comparison to a NARMAX model, previously proposed for load identification, demonstrated the superiority of the developed LMN approach, in terms of speed and accuracy.

As the final point to mention, despite the presented promising results the proposed LMN may deteriorate if the load dynamics varies through the time, due to the connection/disconnection of the loads or serious grid reconfiguration. The remedy to this difficulty would be employing online learning techniques for estimating the parameters of the local models, which will be pursued by the authors in near future.

APPENDIX

This Appendix presents the Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy model interpretation of the proposed LMN in (1). To demonstrate this equivalence, consider a Takagi-Sugeno system with p inputs u_1, \dots, u_p

M fuzzy rules:

$$\text{if } u_1 \text{ is } A_{i1} \text{ and } \dots \text{ and } u_p \text{ is } A_{ip} \text{ then } y_i = h_i(\underline{u}) \quad (\text{A1})$$

where $i = 1, \dots, M$ is the rule index and A_{ij} denote the fuzzy set used for input u_j in rule i . The output of the Takagi-Sugeno system, defined by (A1) can be calculated by

$$\hat{y} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M \mu_i(\underline{u}) h_i(\underline{u})}{\sum_{i=1}^M \mu_i(\underline{u})} \quad (\text{A2})$$

, and the following

where μ_i represents the degree of fulfillment of rule i . By applying the product operator as -norm, μ_i becomes

$$\mu_i(\underline{u}) = \mu_{i1}(u_1) \cdot \mu_{i2}(u_2) \cdot \dots \cdot \mu_{ip}(u_p) \quad (\text{A3})$$

where μ_{ij} denotes the membership degree of input u_j to fuzzy set A_{ij} .

Now, by defining

$$\Phi_i(\underline{u}) = \frac{\mu_i(\underline{u})}{\sum_{i=1}^M \mu_i(\underline{u})} \quad (\text{A4})$$

the Takagi-Sugeno system in (A2) can be re-formulated as

$$\hat{y} = \sum_{i=1}^M h_i(\underline{u}) \Phi_i(\underline{u}). \quad (\text{A5})$$

The similarity between LMN model in (1) and TakagiSugeno model in (A5) is easily perceived.

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